

Some Properties of Force Fields on the Groups of Diffeomorphisms of the flat n -Dimensional Torus, connected with the Notion of Parallelism

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Abstract

Some existence of solution theorems are proved for second order differential inclusions on the groups of diffeomorphisms of a flat n -dimensional torus. The technical tool for the proofs is the use of the notion of parallelism on those groups.

Key words: Flat torus; groups of diffeomorphisms; differential inclusions; parallelism

1 Introduction and preliminaries

We investigate second order differential equations and inclusions on the group $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ of Sobolev H^s -diffeomorphisms of flat n -dimensional torus \mathcal{T}^n , $s > \frac{n}{2} + 1$. The necessary preliminaries on their group and Hilbert manifold structures can be found in [2, 4].

Besides the group structure mentioned above, on $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ there exists an additional structure generated by the global parallelism of the tangent bundle on \mathcal{T}^n . This structure is the main technical tool of our consideration. It is described as follows (see, e.g., [4]).

Definition 1. Introduce the operators:

- (i) $B : T\mathcal{T}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, the projection to the second factor in $T\mathcal{T}^n = \mathcal{T}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n$;
- (ii) $A(m) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow T_m\mathcal{T}^n$, the inverse to B (see (i)) mapping to the tangent space to \mathcal{T}^n at $m \in \mathcal{T}^n$;
- (iii) $Q_g = A(g(m)) \circ B$, a linear isomorphism $Q_g : T_m\mathcal{T}^n \rightarrow T_{g(m)}\mathcal{T}^n$, where $g \in D^s$ and $m \in \mathcal{T}^n$.

The operator Q_e is a one, different from the right shift, that sends every tangent space to the group isomorphically to the tangent space at the unit e . Thus, besides the right-invariant vector fields on $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ there is another class of fields with a property of invariance, this time with respect to the action of operator Q . We call these fields parallel.

Definition 2. A vector field X on $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ is called parallel if at every point $\eta \in D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ its value $X_\eta = Q_\eta X_e$ where $X_e \in T_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$.

Note that the parallel vector field X is invariant with respect to Q_θ for every $\theta \in D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$.

By i we denote an isometric embedding of \mathcal{T}^n to a Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^k for k large enough, that exists by well-known Nash's theorem.

This embedding $i : \mathcal{T}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$ generates the embedding of $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ to the Hilbert space $H^s(\mathcal{T}^n, \mathbb{R}^k)$, which we denote by the same symbol i .

Recall that a tubular neighborhood U of the submanifold $iD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ in $H^s(\mathcal{T}^n, \mathbb{R}^k)$ has the structure of direct product $U = iD^s(\mathcal{T}^n) \times W$, where W is a ball in the space normal to the tangent space $T_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$, $e = id$ is the unit in the group $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. By r we denote the retraction $r : U \rightarrow D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. Thus the tangent spaces to U are represented as $T_\xi U = T_{r\xi} D^s(\mathcal{T}^n) \times T_\xi W$. If $X(\eta)$ is a vector field on $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$, the tangent map Ti sends it into the vector field TiX on $iD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. By symbol \bar{X} we denote the extension of TiX to U of the form $\bar{X}_\xi = (TiX_{r\xi}, 0)$.

On $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ one can introduce a strong Riemannian metric, say, as in [2, 4]. By $dist(\eta, \theta)$ we denote the Riemannian distance between η and θ (i.e., the infimum of curve lengths for curves joining η and θ). Introduce on $TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ the distance d by the formula

$$d((X(\eta)), (Y(\theta))) = dist(\eta, \theta) + \|Q_e X(\eta) - Q_e Y(\theta)\|, \quad (1.1)$$

where the norm in $T_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ is generated by the strong Riemannian metric. Besides, we shall use the distance between the above-mentioned vectors in \mathbb{R}^k after embedding. This distance is denoted by $\|iX(\eta) - iY(\theta)\|$.

Introduce another strong Riemannian metric on $TD_\mu^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ as follows (see [3]). Represent the tangent space $T_{(m,X)} TD_\mu^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ as the direct product of the vertical subspace $\bar{V}_{(m,X)}$ and the space of Live-Civita connection $\bar{H}_{(m,X)}$ of the weak Riemannian metric (see [2]) on $D_\mu^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. For every U and V

from $\bar{V}_{(m,X)}$ define the inner product as $(KU, KV)_\eta^s$ where K is the connector of the above-mentioned Levi-Civita connection and $(\cdot, \cdot)_\eta^s$ is the strong inner product in $T_\eta D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ generated by the strong Riemannian metric. For every X and Y from $\bar{H}_{(m,X)}$ define the inner product as $(T\pi X, T\pi Y)_\eta^s$. Set $\bar{H}_{(m,X)}$ and $\bar{V}_{(m,X)}$ to be orthogonal to each other. Thus, on $TD_\mu^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ a certain strong Riemannian metric is well-defined. The Riemannian distance, i.e., the infimum of the length of curves, connecting the points in TD^s , with respect to the above Riemannian metric, is denoted by d_1 .

Construct the distance $d_2(X, Y)$ on $TTD_\mu^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$, analogous to the distance d on $TD_\mu^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$, by the formula

$$\begin{aligned} d_2(X, Y) = & d(\pi_1 X, \pi_1 Y) + \|Q_e K X_v - Q_e K Y_v\| \\ & + \|Q_e T\pi X_h - Q_e T\pi Y_h\|, \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

where $\pi : TD_\mu^s(M) \rightarrow D_\mu^s(M)$ is the natural projection, X_v and Y_v are the vertical components of X and Y while X_h and Y_h are their horizontal components.

For the metrics $dist$, d , d_1 and d_2 and for the norm $\|\cdot\|$ in $T_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ we shall consider their Kuratowski measures of non-compactness which will be denoted by α_{dist} , α_d , α_{d_1} , α_{d_2} and $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}$, respectively. We refer the reader, say, to [1], where the definitions of measures of non-compactness and of condensing operators are given and the corresponding theory is described in details.

We say that a force field $F(t, m, X)$ is given on a manifold M if in the tangent space $T_m M$ at every $m \in M$ a certain vector $F(t, m, X)$ depending on the time t and the vector $X \in T_m M$, is given. The force fields are right-hand sides of the second order differential equations on manifolds given in terms of covariant derivatives (see, e.g., [4]).

The main aim of the paper is investigation of set-valued force fields and the corresponding second order differential inclusions on the groups of diffeomorphisms of the flat n -dimensional torus with the use of the notion of parallelism. On this base some existence of solution theorems for second order differential inclusions on the above-mentioned groups are obtained.

The definitions and principal facts from the theory of set-valued maps and differential inclusions are contained in [6].

2 Second order differential inclusions

Lemma 1. *Let a set-valued force field $F : [0, l] \times TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n) \rightarrow TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ with convex values satisfy the upper Caratheodory condition and be such that for almost all t for the mapping $A : [0, l] \times TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n) \rightarrow T_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ of the form $A(t, \eta, X) = Q_e F(t, \eta, X)$ and for every bounded set $\Omega \subset D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ the inequality $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}(A(t, \Omega)) \leq g(t) \alpha_d(\Omega)$ holds. Then for almost all t the vector*

field $F(t, \eta, X)$ is k -bounded with respect the measure of non-compactness α_d with the coefficient $1 + g(t)$.

Proof. By the hypothesis for every $\Omega \subset TD^s$, for which $\alpha_d(\Omega)$ is finite, the inequality $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}(A(t, \Omega)) \leq g(t) \alpha_d(\Omega)$ holds. Specify $t \in [0, l]$. Suppose that $\alpha_d(\Omega) = \xi$, i.e., for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a finite cover of Ω by the sets Θ_i with diameters $\xi + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$. Then from the hypothesis it follows that there exists a finite cover of $A(t, \Omega) \subset T_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ by the sets G_j with diameters $g(t) \xi + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$. Consider the set $Q_\eta A(t, \Omega) \subset T_\eta D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. Then the set $\bigcup_{\eta \in \Omega} Q_\eta A(t, \Omega)$ has the natural structure of direct product $\Omega \times A(t, \Omega)$. Consider the set $G_{ij} = \bigcup_{\eta \in \Theta_i} Q_\eta G_j$. The collection of sets G_{ij} forms a finite cover of Γ and the diameter of every such set with respect to the distance d is not greater then $\xi + g(t) \xi + \varepsilon$. Hence $\alpha_d(\Gamma) \leq (1 + g(t)) \xi$. Since $F(t, \Omega) \subset \Gamma$, for almost all t the vector field $F(t, \eta, X)$ is k -bounded with respect to the measure of non-compactness α_d with the coefficient $1 + g(t)$. \square

Lemma 2. *Let the set-valued force field F on $TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ is as in the previous Lemma. Then the vertical lift of this mapping*

$$F^l : [0, l] \times TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n) \rightarrow TTD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$$

is k -bounded with respect to the measures of non-pcompactness α_d and α_{d_2} with the coefficient $2 + g(t)$.

Proof. Specify $t \in [0, l]$. Consider the set $\Theta \subset TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. Let its measure of non-compactness $\alpha_d(\Theta) = \xi$. This means that for every $\varepsilon > 0$ it can be covered by a finite number of sets Θ_i with diameter $\xi + \varepsilon$. Then from the definition of distance d it follows that the set $\pi\Theta$ can be covered by a finite number of sets $\pi\Theta_i$ whose diameter is not greater than $\xi + \varepsilon$, i.e., $\alpha_d(\pi\Theta) \leq \xi$. Then by the hypothesis $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}(A(t, \pi\Theta)) \leq g(t) \xi$, i.e., $(A(t, \pi\Theta)) \subset T_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ can be covered by a finite number of sets G_j with the diameter nit greater than $g(t) \xi + \varepsilon$. By analogy with the proof of the previous Lemma consider the sets $G_{ij}^l = \bigcup_{\theta \in \Theta_i} (Q_{\pi\theta} G_j)^l$. It is evident that the collection of all G_{ij}^l covers the image $F^l(t, \Theta)$. Since we have the finite number of those sets and the diameter of each one is not greater than $2\xi + g(t)\xi + \varepsilon$, the Lemma follows. \square

Introduce the norm $\| \| F^l \| \| = \sup_{y \in F^l} \| \| y \| \|$. Choose an arbitrary point $Z \in TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. Since at every given t the set-valued map F^l is upper semicontinuous, there exists a neighborhood $V'(Z) \subset TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ of the point Z such that for $Y \in V'(Z)$ the relation $\| \| F^l(t, Y) \| \| < \| \| F^l(t, Z) \| \| + C$ holds.

Determine the neighborhood $\tilde{V}(Z) \subset TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ by the formula $\tilde{V} = V \cap V'$ where V is the neighborhood from [3, Theorem 1]. Specify a neighborhood

$D \subset U$ of Z as in [5, Theorem 1.4] such that $r(D) \subset \tilde{V}$. By [5, Theorem 1.4] the retraction r is Lipschitz continuous on D with the constant 2.

Theorem 3. *On the domain D for almost all t the vector field \bar{F}^l is k -bounded with respect to the measure of non-compactness $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}$ with the coefficient*

$$2(2 + g(t)) (1 + a + k(C + \|\|F^l(t, Z)\|\|)).$$

Proof. Consider the set $\Omega \subset D$. Let $\alpha(\Omega) = \xi$. I.e., for every $\varepsilon > 0$ it can be covered by a finite number of sets Ω_i with diameter non greater than $\xi + \varepsilon$. Consider the set $r(\Omega) \subset TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$, where r the retraction mentioned above. By [5, Theorem 1.4] the retraction r is Lipschitz continuous on D with the constant 2 with respect to the norm $\|\cdot\|$ on D and the distance d_1 on $TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. Hence the set $r(\Omega)$ can be covered by a finite number of the sets with diameter not greater than $2\xi + \varepsilon$ with respect to d_1 . Consider the set $F^l(t, r(\Omega)) \subset TTD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. This set can be covered by a finite number of sets with diameter not greater than $2(2 + g(t))\xi + \varepsilon$ with respect to the distance d_2 . Now from Lemma 2 and from the construction of the neighborhoods \tilde{V} and of D it follows that the set $\bar{F}^l(t, \Omega)$ can be covered by a finite number of sets with diameter not greater than $2(2 + g(t))(1 + a + k(C + \|\|F^l(t, Z)\|\|))\xi + \varepsilon$. Hence \bar{F}^l is condensing on D with respect to $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}$ with the coefficient

$$2(2 + g(t)) (1 + a + k(C + \|\|F^l(t, Z)\|\|)). \quad \square$$

Let F be a set-valued force field with convex images on $TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ that satisfies the upper Caratheodory condition. Consider the differential inclusion

$$\frac{\tilde{D}}{dt}\dot{\eta}(t) \in F(t, \eta, \dot{\eta}). \quad (2.1)$$

This problem is reduced to the differential inclusion $\dot{\eta} \in \tilde{S} + F^l$ on $TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ where F^l is the vertical lift of F TO $D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ and \tilde{S} is the geodesic spray of the Levi-Civita connection of the weak metrics. It is known that \tilde{S} is smooth and satisfies the condition $T_\pi \tilde{S}(X) = X$. Consider the extension $\bar{S} : U \rightarrow U$ of $\tilde{S} : TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n) \rightarrow TTD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ defined by the formula $\bar{S}(x) = TjS(r(x))$, $x \in U$.

Theorem 4. *Let the set-valued force field $F : [0, l] \times TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n) \rightarrow TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ with convex images satisfy the upper Caratheodory condition and be such that for almost all t the map $A : [0, l] \times TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n) \rightarrow T_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ of the form $A(t, X) = Q_e F(t, X)$ is k -bounded with respect to the measures of non-compactness α_d and $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}$ with the coefficient $g(t)$. Then for almost all t the vector field $\bar{S} + \bar{F}^l$ is locally k -bounded on a small enough neighborhood U in $TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ with respect to the measures of non-compactness $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}$.*

Proof. By Theorem 3 for almost all $t \in [0, l]$ for every $Z \in TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$ there exists its neighborhood D in U , on which the set-valued force field \bar{F}^l is k -bounded with the coefficient $k = 2(2 + g(t))(1 + a + k(C + \|\|F^l(t, Z)\|\|))$ relative to the measure of non-compactness $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}$. The geodesic spray \tilde{S} is a C^∞ -smooth vector field. The embedding j and the retraction r are S^∞ -smooth as well. Thus the vector field \bar{S} on U is C^∞ smooth and so, in particular, locally Lipschitz continuous. Hence on a small enough neighborhood of the point Z the field \bar{S} is Lipschitz continuous with a certain constant $g > 0$. Without loss of generality one can suppose that D is the above-mentioned neighborhood. By the properties of Kuratowski's measure of non-compactness the sum of locally k -bounded and a locally Lipschitz continuous field is locally k -bounded. Hence the set-valued vector field $\bar{S} + \bar{F}^l$ is locally k -bounded with respect to the measure of non-compactness $\alpha_{\|\cdot\|}$ with the coefficient $k = 2(2 + g(t))(1 + a + k(C + \|\|F^l(t, Z)\|\|)) + g$. \square

Theorem 5. *Let the hypothesis of Theorem 4 are fulfilled and the function $g(t)$ be square integrable on the interval $[0, T]$. Specify a point $Z_0 \in TD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. Suppose that on the closure \bar{D} of a certain neighborhood D of this point the estimate $\|F(t, X)\| < f(t)$, $X \in \bar{D}$ holds, where $f(t) > 0$ is a real function that is square integrable on $[0, l]$. Then the initial value problem (2.1) with initial condition $\eta(0) = \pi Z_0, \dot{\eta}(0) = Z_0$ has a local solution.*

Proof. Without loss of generality one can consider D as a neighborhood from the proof of Theorem 4. Consider the initial value problem $\gamma'(t) \in \bar{S} + \bar{F}^l$ on U with the initial condition $\gamma(0) \in Z_0 \in jT_e D^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. Under the hypothesis, the function

$$k(t) = 2(2 + g(t))(1 + a + k(C + \|\|F^l(t, Z)\|\|)) + g$$

is integrable on $[0, l]$. Then from Theorem 4 it follows that the right-hand side of the latter differential inclusion satisfies the conditions of [6, Theorem 5.2.1] and so this initial value problem has a local solution. By analogy with [5, Theorem 2.4] one can easily prove that this solution belongs to $jTD^s(\mathcal{T}^n)$. Inclusion (2.1) is reduced to the inclusion with right-hand side $\tilde{S} + F^l$. This means that $\pi\gamma(t)$ satisfies inclusion (2.1). \square

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